

Chebyshev via averaging

Adolf Cusmariu

Email: adolcus@gmail.com

The **Chebyshev Sum Inequality (CSI)** states that for non-increasing sequences/vectors

$$X = \{x_j\}, \quad Y = \{y_j\}$$

the average of their inner product dominates the product of their averages; that is

$$\frac{1}{n}(X, Y) = \frac{1}{n} \sum x_k y_k \geq \frac{1}{n} \sum x_k \frac{1}{n} \sum y_k$$

or what is the same

$$(X, Y) = \sum x_k y_k \geq \frac{1}{n} (\sum x_k) (\sum y_k)$$

Let $U = \{1_j\}$ be the vector of all 1's. The inequality may be written more elegantly as

$$(X, Y) \geq \frac{1}{n} (X, U)(Y, U)$$

which reverses for non-decreasing sequences.

To use the averaging method **[1],[2],[3]**, let's first check that **CSI** actually holds for two numbers.

Since

$$x_1 \geq x_2 \quad \text{and} \quad y_1 \geq y_2$$

$$x_1(y_1 - y_2) \geq x_2(y_1 - y_2)$$

so swapping places yields

$$x_1 y_1 + x_2 y_2 \geq x_2 y_1 + x_1 y_2$$

and doubling the left-hand-side leads to the result:

$$2(x_1 y_1 + x_2 y_2) \geq x_2 y_1 + x_1 y_2 + x_1 y_1 + x_2 y_2 = (x_1 + x_2)(y_1 + y_2)$$

or

$$\frac{1}{2}(x_1 y_1 + x_2 y_2) \geq \frac{1}{2}(x_1 + x_2) \frac{1}{2}(y_1 + y_2)$$

Let's do the case for three numbers:

$$\frac{1}{3}(x_1 y_1 + x_2 y_2 + x_3 y_3) \geq \frac{1}{3}(x_1 + x_2 + x_3) \frac{1}{3}(y_1 + y_2 + y_3)$$

The general case will follow easily.

Thus

$$x_1y_1 + x_2y_2 + x_3y_3 = \frac{1}{2}(x_1y_1 + x_2y_2) + \frac{1}{2}(x_2y_2 + x_3y_3) + \frac{1}{2}(x_3y_3 + x_1y_1) \geq \\ \geq \frac{1}{2}(x_1 + x_2)\frac{1}{2}(y_1 + y_2) + \frac{1}{2}(x_2 + x_3)\frac{1}{2}(y_2 + y_3) + \frac{1}{2}(x_1 + x_3)\frac{1}{2}(y_1 + y_3)$$

by an application of **CSI** for two numbers; written more suggestively, this sum is

$$\frac{1}{2}(1x_1 + 1x_2 + 0x_3)\frac{1}{2}(1y_1 + 1y_2 + 0y_3) + \\ \frac{1}{2}(0x_1 + 1x_2 + 1x_3)\frac{1}{2}(0y_1 + 1y_2 + 1y_3) + \\ \frac{1}{2}(1x_1 + 0x_2 + 1x_3)\frac{1}{2}(1y_1 + 0y_2 + 1y_3)$$

to show explicitly how the mix of **I**ntity and **S**hift matrices

$$V = \frac{1}{2}(I + S) = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

scales the $X = \{x_j\}$ and $Y = \{y_j\}$ sequences. Thus after one iteration,

$$(X, Y) \geq (VX, VY)$$

Next, average again, and write the above sum as

$$= \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{1}{2}(x_1 + x_2)\frac{1}{2}(y_1 + y_2) + \frac{1}{2}(x_2 + x_3)\frac{1}{2}(y_2 + y_3) \right\} + \\ \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{1}{2}(x_2 + x_3)\frac{1}{2}(y_2 + y_3) + \frac{1}{2}(x_1 + x_3)\frac{1}{2}(y_1 + y_3) \right\} + \\ \frac{1}{2} \left\{ \frac{1}{2}(x_1 + x_3)\frac{1}{2}(y_1 + y_3) + \frac{1}{2}(x_1 + x_2)\frac{1}{2}(y_1 + y_2) \right\}$$

Pairings have been color-coded to help visually the repeat application; the inequality continues as:

$$\geq \frac{1}{4}(x_1 + 2x_2 + x_3)\frac{1}{4}(y_1 + 2y_2 + y_3) + \\ \frac{1}{4}(x_2 + 2x_3 + x_1)\frac{1}{4}(y_2 + 2y_3 + y_1) + \\ \frac{1}{4}(x_3 + 2x_1 + x_2)\frac{1}{4}(y_3 + 2y_1 + y_2)$$

or in shorthand

$$(X, Y) \geq (VX, VY) \geq (V^2X)(V^2Y)$$

and next

$$\geq \frac{1}{8}(2x_1 + 3x_2 + 3x_3)\frac{1}{8}(2y_1 + 3y_2 + 3y_3) + \\ \frac{1}{8}(2x_2 + 3x_3 + 3x_1)\frac{1}{8}(2y_2 + 3y_3 + 3y_1) + \\ \frac{1}{8}(2x_3 + 3x_1 + 3x_2)\frac{1}{8}(2y_3 + 3y_1 + 3y_2)$$

Therefore

$$(X, Y) \geq (VX, VY) \geq (V^2X)(V^2Y) \geq (V^3X)(V^3Y)$$

and so on. Thus by telescoping induction, for any n

$$(X, Y) \geq (V^n X)(V^n Y)$$

Since V is doubly-stochastic

$$\lim_n V^n = (1/3)J$$

where J is the matrix of all 1's. Hence in the limit

$$(X, Y) \geq (1/3)(X, U)(Y, U)$$

as desired.

For longer strings, choose V to match their dimension and repeat.

References

- [1] <https://zenodo.org/records/3549678>
- [2] <https://zenodo.org/records/3953032>
- [3] <https://zenodo.org/records/7724199>